

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Radiation Robust Receiver for Telecom Constellations (3R4TC)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA11-373</i>
General application	<i>Space</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Cyril Botteron, SpacePNT</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Baptiste Marechal, Kevin Fischer</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>2024.11.19</i>
Facility	<i>HEARTS@CERN (IRRAD)</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>8</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Spaceborne GNSS Receivers represent a fundamental technology to warrant a sustainable and secure use of the space environment. GNSS-based orbit determination can support activities such as collision avoidance and debris removal with minimal latency (ensuring prompt reaction time) and a high degree of autonomy (limiting the usage of valuable ground infrastructure). The hardware platform to implement this technology must strike a delicate balance between radiation robustness (supporting longer satellite lifetime and thus minimizing the accumulation of space junk) and cost (enabling adoption on large constellations such as IRIS2).

The approach envisioned by SpacePNT is based on the use of carefully selected EEE components, that must be characterized in terms of radiation tolerance. To achieve this goal, SpacePNT proposes to carry out heavy ions testing on a short list of components that are essential for the development of such hardware platform.

The HEARTS 2024 activity at CERN gives access to a high energy beam. This allows us to test components we had issues during decapsulation process.

The tested components in this session are a DDR and an ADC:

- DDR3_IS46TR16256BL-125KBLA2_SODIMM
- ADC_ADC128S102CIMT_NOPB

Experiment test report

The RADNEXT_CERN_Radiation_Test_Report_ADC_ADC128S102CIMT_NOPB and RADNEXT_CERN_Radiation_Test_Report_DDR3_IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3_SODIMM test reports are provided as in-line in this section.

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RADNEXT_CERN_Radiation_Test_Report_ADC_ADC128S102C1MT_NOPB

Introduction

This document details the SEE radiation report for the ADC128S102C1MT_NOPB.

Device Information

Product description

The ADC128S102C1MT_NOPB is a low-power, eight-channel CMOS 12-bit analog-to-digital converter specified for conversion throughput rates of 500 ksp/s to 1 MSPS. The package is a TSSOP 16 and the device is characterized for operation from -40°C to +105°C.

Device details

Manufacturer's Designation	ADC128S102C1MT_NOPB					
Manufacturer's Name	Texas Instruments					
Manufacturer's Headquarter address:	Dallas, Texas, U.S					
Package Designation:	TSSOP 16					
Component group:	CMOS					
Datasheet Reference:	SNAS298G – AUGUST 2005 –REVISED JANUARY 2015					
Lot code / Date Code:	3022387EM3 / 2304+5					
Country of Origin (CoO):	MY					
Procurement Agent:	Texas Instruments					
TI LOT NUMBER	LOT TRACE CODE	QUANTITY	DATE CODE	WAFER LOT	WAFER LTC	ASSEMBLY SITE
3022387EM3	31A04CU	47	2304+5	2296340CU8	2012616CUA	CU6

Samples identification

DUT name	ADC128S102C1MT_NOPB
Concerned equipment	ADC
Irradiated samples ID	1, 2
Vcc (V)	3.3

Figure 0-1: DUT Identification

Test Setup

Test Description and Facilities

SEE testing is performed according to the SEE Test Plan and the ESCC25100 [Error! Reference source not found.\[RD4\]](#). The SEE test campaign takes place at CERN (Switzerland) on Nov. 19th 2024, as part of the HEARTS@CERN project. The Heavy Ion Facility provides spills of Pb ions on the DUT. For those DUT, the test focuses on SEU, SEL and SEFI. The SEE test is performed as following:

- The DUT is connected on the test equipment
- The test equipment is powered on, voltage, current and temperature are logged
- The DUT is powered on
- The test sequence starts, outputs are logged

In case of issue/error during the test, one of the following actions is taken:

- Continue the test sequence
- Power cycle the DUT and the test board
- Auto delatch

Test Setup Details

Schematic

3.3V_VA and 3.3V_VD are connected together.

Figure 0-1: DUT Schematic

Assembly Drawing

Figure 0-2: DUT Assembly Drawing

Run description

The Run Id	Run start time (UTC)	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm2/mg)	OCP trigger (mA)
3	2024-11-19T11:30:48UTC	1	12.3	150
4	2024-11-19T12:03:43UTC	1	36.3	150
5	2024-11-19T12:48:00UTC	1	26.6	70
6	2024-11-19T14:20:53UTC	2	12.3	70
7	2024-11-19T14:56:11UTC	2	36.3	70
8	2024-11-19T15:37:06UTC	2	26.6	70

Functional Test Description

During the run, the DUT is connected to the uC board, which is running the test software. The R&S HMP4040 power supply provides the 3.3 V to the DUT, through the uC board. The HMP over current protection is enabled to provide a de-latch function, with a software running on the remote PC. The OCP response time is <10 ms and the delatch occurs within the next 1 s. The DUT temperature is monitored with a PT1000 and a DAQ970A+DAQM901A. The RedPitaya board acts as a Single Board Computer to provide a remote access/log of the UART connection of the uC board. The PMOD DA2 daughter board generates a voltage on the channel 1 of the DUT. That signal is either a DC level (between 0 and 3.3V), either a 0.05Hz ramp (0-3.3V).

The error plot is the $\text{abs}(\text{read value} - \text{expected value}) + 1$, in log scale. The +1 is here to avoid $\log(0)$. The log scale is used to see both huge and small errors. An event is considered as an error if there is a current step or an error >10 bits.

Figure 0-3: SEE Test Setup

Experimental results

Sample 1 - Run 3

Figure 0-1 Sample 1 - Run 3 overview

Figure 0-2 Sample 1 - Run 3 Temperature

Run 3 is performed on Sample 1 at 12.3 MeV.cm²/mg. The 3 sections at 11:26, 11:42 and 11:51 correspond to read value of 3.3V, which generate saturation in the DUT. The read value stays at the maximum (4095) without fluctuations. The resulting “error +1” is 1, without noise.

The ~~Figure 0-1~~ ~~Figure 4-1~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading error are reported on the bottom figure.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-2~~ ~~Figure 4-2~~). No heater is used here. The DUT is heated up only during 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg runs.

The fluence is 1010172 ions/cm².

No events are reported during this run.

Sample 1 – Run 4

Figure 0-3 Sample 1 - Run 4 overview

Figure 0-4 Sample 1 - Run 4 Temperature

Run 4 is performed on Sample 1 at 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg. The ~~Figure 0-3~~~~Figure 4-3~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading errors are reported on the bottom figure. The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-4~~~~Figure 4-4~~). The DUT is heated up during those 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg run. The fluence is 896986 ions/cm². The events are reported in ~~Table 0-1~~~~Table 4-1~~.

Event Id	Observations	SEU	SEL	SEFI	Action
1	Current increase Reading stopped			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
2	Current drop at startup Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
3	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
4	Current drop at startup Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
5	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
6	Current drop at startup Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
7	Current increase Reading stopped			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
8	Current drop at startup Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
9	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
10	Current increase Reading stopped			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
11	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
12	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
13	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
14	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
15	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
16	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
17	Current drop at startup Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
18	Current increase Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
19	Current increase Reading stopped			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board

Table 0-1 Sample 1 - Run 4 Events list

Figure 0-5 Sample 1 - Run 4 - Typical Current increase, reading stopped

Figure 0-6 Sample 1 - Run 4 – Typical Current drop at startup, read value mismatch

Figure 0-7 Sample 1 - Run 4 – Typical Current increase, read value mismatch

Figure 0-8 Sample 1 - Run 4 – Typical Read value mismatch

Sample 1 – Run 5

Figure 0-9 Sample 1 - Run 5 overview

Figure 0-10 Sample 1 - Run 5 Temperature

Run 5 is performed on Sample 1 at 26.6 MeV.cm²/mg. An issue occurs on the accelerator around 2024/11/19-13:03:00 UTC. The run was in pause for ~25min.

The ~~Figure 0-9~~~~Figure 4-9~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading errors are reported on the bottom figure.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-10~~~~Figure 4-10~~). No heater is used here. The DUT is heated up only during 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg runs.

The fluence is 1008564 ions/cm².

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-2~~~~Table 4-2~~.

Event Id	Observations	SEU	SEL	SEFI	Action
1	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
2	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
3	Read value mismatch			x	Power cycle the DUT and the test board
4	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
5	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
6	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence

Table 0-2 Sample 1 - Run 5 Events list

Figure 0-11 Sample 1 - Run 5 – Typical Read value mismatch

Sample 2 – Run 6

Figure 0-12 Sample 2 - Run 6 overview

Figure 0-13 Sample 2 - Run 6 Temperature

Run 6 is performed on Sample 2 at 12.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-12~~Figure 4-42 (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading errors are reported on the bottom figure.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-13~~Figure 4-13). No heater is used here. The DUT is heated up only during 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg runs.

The fluence is 1011201 ions/cm².

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-3~~Table 4-3.

Event Id	Observations	SEU	SEL	SEFI	Action
1	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence
2	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence

Table 0-3 Sample 2 - Run 6 Events list

Figure 0-14 Sample 2 - Run 6 – Typical Read value mismatch

Sample 2 – Run 7

Figure 0-15 Sample 2 - Run 7 overview

Figure 0-16 Sample 2 - Run 7 Temperature

Run 7 is performed on Sample 2 at 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-15~~~~Figure 4-15~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading errors are reported on the bottom figure.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-16~~~~Figure 4-16~~). The DUT is heated up to 60°C during the second half of this run. The heater's power supply was off during the first half.

The fluence is 1013023 ions/cm².

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-4~~~~Table 4-4~~. This run is not taken into account because the SEFI and the SEU events cannot be distinguished.

<i>Event Id</i>	<i>Observations</i>	<i>SEU</i>	<i>SEL</i>	<i>SEFI</i>	<i>Action</i>
1	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
2	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
3	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
4	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
5	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
6	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
7	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
8	<i>Current increase</i> <i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
9	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
10	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
11	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
12	<i>Current increase</i> <i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
13	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
14	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
15	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
16	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>
17	<i>Read value mismatch</i>				<i>Auto delatch</i>

Table 0-4 Sample 2 - Run 7 Events list

Figure 0-17 Sample 2 - Run 7 – Typical Current increase, read value mismatch

Figure 0-18 Sample 2 - Run 7 – Typical Read value mismatch

Sample 2 – Run 8

Figure 0-19 Sample 2 - Run 8 overview

Figure 0-20 Sample 2 - Run 8 Temperature

Run 8 is performed on Sample 2 at 26.6 MeV.cm²/mg.
 The [Figure 0-19](#)[Figure 4-19](#) (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The heavy ion spills and the reading errors are reported on the bottom figure.
 The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side ([Figure 0-20](#)[Figure 4-20](#)). No heater is used here.
 The DUT is heated up only during 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg runs.
 The fluence is 1029174 ions/cm².
 The events are reported in [Table 0-4](#)[Table 4-4](#). The event is ignored because the relative error is less than 1% (41 bits).

Event Id	Observations	SEU	SEL	SEFI	Action
1	Read value mismatch	x			Continue the test sequence

Table 0-5 Sample 2 - Run 8 Events list

Figure 0-21 Sample 2 - Run 8 – Typical Read value mismatch (ignored)

Conclusion

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ²)
3	1	12.3	1010172	0	9.89930e-07
4	1	36.3	896986	6	6.68907e-06
5	1	26.6	1008564	5	4.95754e-06
6	2	12.3	1011201	2	1.97785e-06
7	2	36.3	1013023	NA	NA
8	2	26.6	1029174	1	9.71653e-07

Table 0-1 SEU

Figure 0-1 SEU Weibull curve

Parameter	Unit	Value
W	.	2.309e+1
S	.	4.753e+0
Limit Cross-section	cm ²	6.707e-6
LET Threshold	MeV.cm ² /mg	1e-3

Table 0-2 SEU Weibull parameters

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ²)
3	1	12.3	1010172	0	9.89930e-07
4	1	36.3	896986	0	1.11484e-06
5	1	26.6	1008564	0	9.91509e-07
6	2	12.3	1011201	0	9.88923e-07
7	2	36.3	1013023	NA	NA
8	2	26.6	1029174	0	9.71653e-07

Table 0-3 SEL

No SEL were detected, so no Weibull fit has been carried out.

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ²)
3	1	12.3	1010172	0	9.89930e-07
4	1	36.3	896986	13	1.44930e-05
5	1	26.6	1008564	1	9.91509e-07
6	2	12.3	1011201	0	9.88923e-07
7	2	36.3	1013023	NA	NA
8	2	26.6	1029174	0	9.71653e-07

Table 0-4 SEFI

Figure 0-2 SEFI Weibull curve

Parameter	Unit	Value
W	.	2.705e+1
S	.	6.602e+0
Limit Cross-section	cm ²	1.451e-5
LET Threshold	MeV.cm ² /mg	1.000e-3

Table 0-5 SEFI Weibull parameters

RADNEXT_CERN_Radiation_Test_Report_DDR3_IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3_SODIMM

Introduction

This document details the SEE radiation report for the IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3.

Device Information

Product description

The IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3 is a DDR3 SDRAM memory chip. The package is a 96 balls BGA package and the device is temperature range is: 0°C to 95°C.

Device details

<i>Manufacturer's Designation</i>	IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3						
<i>Manufacturer's Name</i>	<i>ISSI, Integrated Silicon Solution Inc</i>						
<i>Manufacturer's Headquarter address:</i>	<i>Milpitas, 1623 Buckeye Dr., Milpitas, CA 95035</i>						
<i>Package Designation:</i>	96-TWBGA						
<i>Component group:</i>	CMOS						
<i>Datasheet Reference:</i>	IS43/46TR16256ECL, Rev. D, 01/10/2024						
<i>Lot code / Date Code:</i>	MSF368000Y12 / 2408						
<i>Country of Origin (CoO):</i>	TW						
<i>Procurement Agent:</i>	AVNET						
Line	Item number	Item description	Config	Unit	Quantity	Price Curr.	Net extension
1	IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3 IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3	IC SDRAM	256Mx16	EA	3	5.75302 USD	17.26
	CPN: Data Code.: 2408	IC Sales ID:C01SO-200008599-1.00 LOT#:MSF368000Y12		WFID:			

Samples identification

DUT name	IS46TR16256ECL-125LB2LA3
Concerned equipment	DDR
Irradiated samples ID	1, 2
Vcc (V)	1.5
Vtt, Vref (V)	3.3

Figure 0-1: DUT Identification

Test Setup

Test Description and Facilities

SEE testing is performed according to the SEE Test Plan and the ESCC25100 **Error! Reference source not found.[RD4]**. The SEE test campaign take place at CERN (Switzerland) on Nov. 19th 2024, as part of the HEARTS@CERN project. The Heavy Ion Facility provides spills of Pb ions on the DUT. For those DUT, the test focuses on SEU, SEL and SEFI. The SEE test is performed as following:

- The DUT is connected on the test equipment
- The test equipment is powered on, voltage, current and temperature are logged
- The DUT is powered on
- The test sequence starts, outputs are logged

In case of issue/error during the test, one of the following actions is taken:

- Continue the test sequence
- Restart the test sequence
- Power cycle the DUT
- Power cycle the DUT and the test board
- Auto delatch

Test Setup Details

Schematic

Figure 0-1: DUT Schematic

Assembly Drawing

Figure 0-2: DUT Assembly Drawing

Run description

The Run Id	Run start time (UTC)	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm2/mg)	Fluence (ions/cm^2)
9	2024-11-19T17:15:49UTC	1	12.3	103611
10	2024-11-19T17:47:10UTC	1	26.6	83122
11	2024-11-19T18:29:34UTC	1	26.6	511374
12	2024-11-19T19:19:07UTC	1	36.3	521827
13	2024-11-19T20:19:42UTC	2	36.3	511302
14	2024-11-19T20:39:52UTC	2	26.6	531895
15	2024-11-19T20:55:05UTC	2	12.3	442272

Functional Test Description

During the run, the DUT is connected to the zc706 evaluation board, which is running the test software. The R&S HMP4040 power supply provides the 1.5-V VCC to the DUT on the channel 1 and the zc706 on the channel 2. The VTTREF and VTT are provided by the zc706 through the sodimm connector. The HMP over current protection is enabled to provide a de-latch function, with a software running on the remote PC. The OCP response time is <10 ms and the delatch occurs within the next 1 s. The DUT

temperature is monitored with a PT1000 and a DAQ970A+DAQM901A.

The test executes the following steps:

- Initialize offset=0
- Loop on offset up to 64 MB
 - o Write 256 kB of 0x5555 from offset
 - o Read it twice and compare
 - o Increment offset by 256 kB

The tested memory size is reduced to 64 MB (512 MB available) to increase the cycle time and get more than 4 write operations on a memory cell.

After each run, a 'stuck bits' test is performed by:

- At the end of the run, write the full memory with 0x0000, then read the memory
- At the end of the run, write the full memory with 0xffff, then read the memory
- Reboot the board, write the full memory with 0x0000, then read the memory
- Reboot the board, write the full memory with 0xffff, then read the memory

The number of incorrect bits is reported in the following sections.

Figure 0-3: SEE Test Setup

Experimental results

Sample 1 - Run 9

Figure 0-1 Sample 1 - Run 9 overview

Figure 0-2 Sample 1 - Run 9 Temperature

Run 9 is performed on Sample 1 at 12.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-1~~~~Figure 4-4~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 103611 ions/cm².

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-2~~~~Figure 4-2~~). No heater is used here.

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-1~~~~Table 4-4~~

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEU	Writing bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	0

Table 0-1 Sample 1 - Run 9 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in ~~Table 0-2~~~~Table 4-2~~.

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	569
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	449
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-2 Sample 1 - Run 9 Stuck bits

Sample 1 - Run 10

Figure 0-3 Sample 1 - Run 10 overview

Figure 0-4 Sample 1 - Run 10 Temperature

Run 10 is performed on Sample 1 at 26.6 MeV.cm²/mg.

The [Figure 0-3](#)~~Figure 4-3~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 83122 ions/cm².

A current increase is visible at 17:51UTC, with no functional impact.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side ([Figure 0-4](#)~~Figure 4-4~~). No heater is used here.

The events are reported in [Table 0-3](#)~~Table 4-3~~.

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip 0x5555 pattern offset 11075584 position 0	Continue the test sequence	1
SEU	Writing bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	0

Table 0-3 Sample 1 - Run 10 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in [Table 0-4](#)~~Table 4-4~~.

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	212
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	106
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-4 Sample 1 - Run 10 Stuck bits

Sample 1 - Run 11

Figure 0-5 Sample 1 - Run 11 overview

Figure 0-6 Sample 1 - Run 11 Temperature

Run 11 is performed on Sample 1 at 26.6 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-5~~~~Figure 4-5~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 511374 ions/cm².

A current increase is visible at 18:41UTC, with no functional impact.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-6~~~~Figure 4-6~~). No heater is used here.

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-5~~~~Table 4-5~~.

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEU	Writing bitflip 0xAAAA pattern offset 15466496 positions 0, 1	Continue the test sequence	2
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	2

Table 0-5 Sample 1 - Run 11 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in ~~Table 0-6~~~~Table 4-6~~.

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	16355
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-6 Sample 1 - Run 11 Stuck bits

Sample 1 - Run 12

Figure 0-7 Sample 1 - Run 12 overview

Figure 0-8 Sample 1 - Run 12 Temperature

Run 12 is performed on Sample 1 at 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-7~~~~Figure 4-7~~ (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 521827 ions/cm².

3 current increases are visible at 19:22UTC, 19:36UTC and 19:38UTC, with no functional impact.

A current decrease is also visible at 19:34UTC.

The temperature of the DUT is monitored along-side (~~Figure 0-8~~~~Figure 4-8~~). No heater is used here.

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-7~~~~Table 4-7~~.

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip 0x5555 pattern offset 1048576 position 0	Continue the test sequence	1
SEU	Writing bitflip 0xAAAA pattern offset 4128768 position 0 0x5555 pattern offset 65536 position 0 0x5555 pattern offset 65536 position 0 0x5555 pattern offset 65536 position 0	Continue the test sequence	4
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	0

Table 0-7 Sample 1 - Run 12 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in Table 0-8~~Table 4-8~~.

Form

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-8 Sample 1 - Run 12 Stuck bits

Sample 2 - Run 13

Figure 0-9 Sample 2 - Run 13 overview

Run 13 is performed on Sample 2 at 36.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The ~~Figure 0-9~~Figure-4-9 (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 511302 ions/cm².

A current increase is visible at 20:21UTC with no functional impact.

A current decrease is also visible at 19:34UTC.

The temperature of the DUT is not available due to recording errors. No heater is used here.

The events are reported in ~~Table 0-9~~Table-4-9.

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip 0xYYYY pattern offset xxxx position xxx	Continue the test sequence	0
SEU	Writing bitflip 0xYYYY pattern offset xxxx position xxx	Continue the test sequence	0
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips 0xAAAA pattern offset 11796480 338 bits mis-wrote (positions 0, 3, 20, 54, 68, 95, 116, 130, 145, 150, 176, 182, 210, 212, 225, 229, 240, 259, 272, 278, 308, 322, 326, 386, 406, 417, 422, 432, 438, 448, 454, 468, 480, 502, 513, 518, 544, 550, 592, 608, 625, 642, 645, 658, 722, 724, 738, 742, 770, 788, 801, 804, 848, 852, 870, 883, 900, 914, 916, 929, 946, 948, 962, 976, 1040, 1046, 1088, 1104, 1110, 1122, 1124, 1135, 1139, 1172, 1204, 1218, 1220, 1238, 1248, 1252, 1264, 1284, 1295, 1314, 1316, 1328, 1332, 1344, 1360, 1364, 1376, 1380, 1391, 1408, 1426, 1428, 1440, 1462, 1478, 1490...) 0x5555 pattern offset 12779520 64 bits mis-wrote (positions 0 to 63) 0x5555 pattern	Continue the test sequence	3

	offset 5767168 1693 bits mis-read (positions 0, 2, 4, 6, 16, 18, 22, 32, 33, 34, 36, 38, 48, 50, 52, 54, 16386, 16388, 16390, 16400, 16402, 16403, 16406, 16415, 16416, 16418, 16422, 16432, 16434, 16436, 16438, 32768, 32770, 32771, 32774, 32784, 32786, 32787, 32790, 32800, 32801, 32802, 32806, 32818, 32820, 32822, 49152, 49154, 49156, 49158, 49168, 49170, 49171, 49174, 49184, 49185, 49186, 49190, 49200, 49201, 49202, 49204, 49206, 65536, 65538, 65540, 65542, 65552, 65554, 65555, 65558, 65568, 65569, 65570, 65574, 65586, 65588, 65590, 81920, 81922, 81924, 81925, 81926, 81936, 81938, 81942, 81952, 81953, 81954, 81958, 81968, 81970, 81972, 81974, 98304, 98306, 98308, 98310, 98320, 98322...)		
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	1

Table 0-9 Sample 2 - Run 13 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in Table 0-10~~Table 4-10~~.

Form

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-10 Sample 1 - Run 13 Stuck bits

Sample 2 - Run 14

Figure 0-10 Sample 2 - Run 14 overview

Run 14 is performed on Sample 2 at 26.6 MeV.cm²/mg.

The [Figure 0-10](#)[Figure 4-10](#)(top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 531895 ions/cm².

A current increase is visible at 20:21UTC with no functional impact.

A current decrease is also visible at 19:34UTC.

The temperature of the DUT is not available due to recording errors. No heater is used here.

The events are reported in [Table 0-11](#)[Table 4-11](#).

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEU	Writing bitflip 0x5555 pattern offset 15466496 positions 0, 1	Continue the test sequence	1
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	0

Table 0-11 Sample 2 - Run 14 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in Table 0-12~~Table 4-12~~.

Form

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-12 Sample 1 - Run 14 Stuck bits

Sample 2 - Run 15

Figure 0-11 Sample 2 - Run 15 overview

Run 14 is performed on Sample 2 at 12.3 MeV.cm²/mg.

The [Figure 0-11](#)[Figure 4-11](#) (top) shows the voltage/current at the HMP4040 output. The test cycles are visible on the current trace with a 55mA to 52mA cycling. The heavy ion spills and the total number of SEU/SEFI of all cycles are reported on the bottom figure.

The total fluence is 442272 ions/cm².

A current increase is visible at 20:21UTC with no functional impact.

A current decrease is also visible at 19:34UTC.

The temperature of the DUT is not available due to recording errors. No heater is used here.

The events are reported in [Table 0-13](#)[Table 4-13](#).

Type of Event	Observations	Recovery Action	Count
SEU	Reading bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEU	Writing bitflip	Continue the test sequence	0
SEL	Latchup reported by the power supply	Auto delatch	0
SEFI	More than 50 bitflips	Continue the test sequence	0
SEFI	Test stuck	Power cycle the DUT and the test board	0

Table 0-13 Sample 2 - Run 15 Events list

The 'stuck bits' test results are reported in Table 0-14~~Table 4-14~~.

Test	Count
At the end of the run, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
At the end of the run, fill with 0xffff, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0x0000, then read	0
After a reboot, fill with 0xffff, then read	0

Table 0-14 Sample 1 - Run 15 Stuck bits

Conclusion

The SEU cross section has been normalised per bit, accounting for the tested memory size (64 MB = 64 * 1024 * 1024 * 8 bit).

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ² / bit)
9	1	12.3	103611	0	1.44E-13
10	1	26.6	83122	1	1.79E-13
11	1	26.6	511374	2	5.83E-14
12	1	36.3	521827	5	1.43E-13
13	2	36.3	511302	0	2.91E-14
14	2	26.6	531895	1	2.80E-14
15	2	12.3	442272	0	3.37E-14

Table 0-~~15~~ SEU

Since no SEU were detected at 12.3 MeV.cm²/mg the cross-section can be conservatively approximated as a flat distribution with a constant value of $\sigma_{SEU} = 2E-13$ cm² / bit.

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ²)
9	1	12.3	103611	0	9.65148e-06
10	1	26.6	83122	0	1.20305e-05
11	1	26.6	511374	0	1.95552e-06
12	1	36.3	521827	0	1.91634e-06
13	2	36.3	511302	0	1.95579e-06
14	2	26.6	531895	0	1.88007e-06
15	2	12.3	442272	0	2.26105e-06

Table 0-162 SEL

No SEL was detected, and therefore no Weibull fit is possible.

Run Id	Sample Id	LET (MeV.cm ² /mg)	Fluence (ions/cm ²)	Event count	Cross Section (cm ²)
9	1	12.3	103611	0	9.65148e-06
10	1	26.6	83122	0	1.20305e-05
11	1	26.6	511374	2	3.91103e-06
12	1	36.3	521827	0	1.91634e-06
13	2	36.3	511302	4	7.82317e-06
14	2	26.6	531895	0	1.88007e-06
15	2	12.3	442272	0	2.26105e-06

Table 0-173 SEFI

Given the low amount of SET detected, it is not possible to obtain a reliable estimate for a Weibull fit. The SEFI cross-section can be conservatively approximated as a flat distribution with a constant value of $\sigma_{SEFI} = 1E-5 \text{ cm}^2$.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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